

Synthesis, crystal structure, DFT calculations and superoxide dismutase activity of copper(II) complex with pyridine-2-carboxylic acid

Ram N. Patel^{*a}, Yogendra Pratap Singh^a, Yogendra Singh^a and Raymond J. Butcher^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, A. P. S. University, Rewa-486 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : rnp64@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Inorganic and Structural Chemistry, Howard University, Washington DC, 22031 USA

Manuscript received online 01 October 2015, accepted 15 December 2015

Abstract : Copper(II) complexes with pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (2-pca) has been synthesized and characterized using various physicochemical methods. The structure of this complex has been solved by X-ray crystallographic methods. The coordination geometry of the copper(II) is very close to square planar. The supra molecular architecture of complex is totally guided by H-bonding. The molecular structures and spectral properties of the ligand and its complex with comparison have been explained by DFT and TD-DFT calculations. The electronic excitation energies of this complex calculated at TD-DFT levels are in agreement with value deduced from the experimental UV-Visible spectra. Superoxide dismutase activity of this complex has also been measured.

Keywords : Supra-molecular Cu^{II} complex, IR, UV-Visible, ESR and CV spectra, TD-DFT calculations, superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity.

Introduction

Copper(II) carboxylates are structurally a very diverse group of coordination compounds due to the various coordination modes of the carboxylato ligands^{1,2}. Polynuclear complexes of copper(II) with the carboxylate as a bridging group have been extensively studied in view of interesting magnetic properties³⁻⁵. It is well known that the carboxylate group is able to create hydrogen bonds leading to the formation of supramolecular networks which play an important role in the transmission of magnetic interactions. This particular interest has also recently been focused on the development of supramolecular structures created by hydrogen bonds. Non-covalent interactions, such as hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic, steric repulsion, aromatic ring stacking and electrostatic interactions play important roles in chemical reactions, molecular recognition and regulating biochemical processes⁶⁻⁸. Pyridine-2-carboxylic acid is an isomer of nicotinic acid and is one of the most important chelating agents in the human body. During digestion it is secreted to the intestine and is used as a complexing agent (bio-ligand) in the absorption of essential metals^{9,10}. The quantum chemical studies carried out using the density functional theory (DFT) have

becomes an increasingly useful tool for theoretical studies. The success of DFT is mainly due to the fact that it describes the small molecules more reliably. In the recent past computational methods based on density functional theory (DFT) has been widely used. Molecular geometries for copper(II) complex with 2-pca have been investigated by using B3LYP method with 6-31G(d,p) and LANL2DZ basis sets. NPA atomic charge distributions on complexes and donor atoms of ligands are calculated at the B3LYP/LANL2DZ level. Electronic excitation energies for mentioned complex have been obtained by using TD-DFT/B3LYP method with LANL2DZ basis set in gas phase. To show the existence of intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) with in molecular system, energy of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) levels and the molecular electrostatic surface potential (MESP) energy surface studies are manipulated by DFT¹¹.

Recently some examples of structurally characterized copper(II) complexes containing 2-pca have been reported in the literature^{3,4,12-15}. In order to obtain mimicry of metalloprotein active sites, we decided to use bioligands. Using pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (2-pca), we have syn-

thesized and characterized two polynuclear copper(II) monomer complex using various physicochemical techniques. The bioactivity properties, such as superoxide dismutase activity of $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was also studied and discussed in detail.

Results and discussion

Single crystal X-ray diffraction :

The copper complexes were structurally characterized using single-crystal X-ray diffraction. Crystallographic data and structure refinement parameters are summarized in Table 1. Selected bond lengths and angles are listed in

Table 1. Summarized crystallographic data and refinement parameters for $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_6$
Formula weight	343.78
Temperature (K)	120(2) K
Wavelength (Å)	1.54184 Å
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
Unit cell dimensions	
<i>a</i> (Å)	5.0958(4)
<i>b</i> (Å)	7.5208(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	9.0842(7)
α (°)	75.948(6)
β (°)	85.088(6)
γ (°)	72.134(6)
Volume (Å ³)	321.42(4)
Z	1
Density (calculated) (Mg/m ³)	1.776
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	2.715
F(000)	175
Theta range for data collection	5.019 to 75.980°
Index ranges	$-6 < h < 5$, $-7 < k < 9$, $-11 < l < 10$
Reflections collected	2209
Independent reflections	1329 [R(int) = 0.0282]
Completeness to theta = 67.500°	99.8%
Absorption correction	Semi-empirical from equivalents
Max. and min. transmission	1.00000 and 0.70572
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²
Data/restraints/parameters	1329/3/105
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.072
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	R1 = 0.0537, wR2 = 0.1425
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.0555, wR2 = 0.1448
Extinction coefficient	n/a
Largest diff. peak and hole	1.512 and -1.021 e.Å ⁻³

Table 2. Complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystallizes as blue crystals in the Triclinic crystal system having space group P-1 with four molecules in the unit cell. The ORTEP view of $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is given in Fig. 1. X-Ray analysis shows that copper(II) in $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is coordinated by two nitrogen atoms and one oxygen atom thus forming chelated having two fused five-membered rings. The equatorial plane is composed of the oxygen and nitrogen atoms of the bis chelating ligand coordinating through pyridine nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen atoms. The second carboxylate oxygen atom is not involved in the coordination to the metal ion. The ligand is coordinated meridional and would be perpendicular in idealized square planar. The value of *trans* angle are O(1)#1-Cu-O(1) : 180(13)° and N(1)#1-Cu-N(1) : 180(13)° and *cis* angle are O(1)-Cu-N(1)#1 : 96.23(10)° and O(1)#1-Cu-N(1) : 96.23(10)°. The Cu-N and Cu-O distance of 1.960(3) Å and 1.946(2) Å respectively these values are agree well with those found in other square planar copper(II) complexes²³⁻²⁵ but the apical distances are very long [Cu...O(2)B, and Cu...O(2)C = 2.737(4) Å]²⁶, while the Cu-O(1), O#(1)A distances are identical (1.946(2) Å). Each carboxylate group bridges two copper(II) ions through its O(2) oxygen atom, resulting in non-planarity of the Cu-O-C-O-Cu(A) fragment. The bridging pathway is asymmetric not only in its conformation but also with respect to the C-O bond lengths. The crystal structure of compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is stabilized by two type of weak hydrogen bonds of the C-H...O and O-H...O type in accordance with the well-known ability of carboxylate moieties to generate hydrogen-bonding motifs in complexes. The crystal packing is shown in Fig. 2. These hydrogen bond interactions (Table 3), lead to the formation of a 2D sheet structure.

Electrochemistry :

Cyclic voltammograms for one step reduction of $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in DMSO (glassy-carbon electrode) is shown in Fig. 3. Electrochemical data is shown in Table 4. An electron transfer property of the complex was studied in 3×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ DMSO by cyclic voltammetry. Fig. 3 voltammograms of CV is shown in complex exhibit one-step redox in DMSO at RT in nitrogen atmosphere. Voltammograms consist of two well-separated peaks, one cathodic peak potential (E_{pc}) and one anodic peak potential (E_{pa}). This reduction is irreversible with a peak-to-

Table 2. Experimental and calculated bond lengths [Å] and angles [°] for [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O

Connectivity	Expt.	Calcd.	Connectivity	Expt.	Calcd.
Cu-O(1)#1	1.946(2)	1.8683	Cu-N(1)#1	1.960(3)	1.8683
Cu-O(1)	1.946(2)	1.8672	Cu-N(1)	1.960(3)	1.8672
Cu-O(2)#2	2.699(2)		Cu-O(2)#3	2.699(2)	
O(1)#1-Cu-O(1)	180.0(13)	180.0	O(1)#1-Cu-N(1)#1	83.77(10)	89.8068
O(1)-Cu-N(1)#1	96.23(10)	90.1932	O(1)#1-Cu-N(1)	96.23(10)	90.1932
O(1)-Cu-N(1)	83.77(10)	89.8068	N(1)#1-Cu-N(1)	180.00(13)	180.0
O(1)#1-Cu-O(2)#2	94.75(8)		N(1)#1-Cu-O(2)#2	90.69(9)	
O(1)-Cu-O(2)#2	85.25(8)		N(1)-Cu-O(2)#2	89.31(9)	
O(1)#1-Cu-O(2)#3	85.25(8)		O(1)-Cu-O(2)#3	94.75(8)	
N(1)#1-Cu-O(2)#3	89.31(9)		N(1)-Cu-O(2)#3	90.69(9)	
O(2)#2-Cu-O(2)#3	180.0		C(6)-O(1)-Cu	114.50(19)	

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms : #1 -x, -y+2, -z+1, #2 -x+1, -y+2, -z+1, #3 x-1, y, z.

Fig. 1. ORTEP view of the complex [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O.

peak separation of 123 ± 10 mV and the cathodic peak current (I_{pc}) is greater than anodic peak current (I_{pa}). The complex shows one reduction peaks corresponding to Cu^{II}-Cu^I. Although the voltammogram shows one reduction peak is -890 mV. The one-electron nature of this reduction has been established by comparing its current with that of a standard ferrocene/ferrocenium couple under the experimental condition. The pertinent redox couple is represented in the following one electron transfer :

Fig. 2. 2D supramolecular architecture of [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O.

Such electrochemistry for square planar copper(II) complexes is earlier reported¹⁵.

Magnetic moment :

Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurement has been made for powdered sample. The effective magnetic moment of 1.83 ± 0.05 BM is close to the values for copper(II) complexes without interactions²⁷ and is quite close values for other copper(II) complexes the magnetic moment value is suggestive of ideal square planar complexes²⁷.

Table 3. Distances [Å] and angles [°] of the hydrogen bonds interactions for [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O

D-H...A	d(D-H)	d(H...A)	d(D...A)	<(DHA)
O(1W)-H(1W1)...O(2)	0.82(2)	2.10(2)	2.906(4)	167(6)
O(1W)-H(1W2)...O(1W)#4	0.81(2)	2.18(8)	2.826(6)	136(11)
C(1)-H(1A)...O(1)#1	0.95	2.64	3.128(4)	112.3
C(4)-H(4A)...O(2)#5	0.95	2.36	3.196(4)	147.0

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms: #1 -x, -y+2, -z+1, #2 -x+1, -y+2, -z+1, #3 x-1, y, z, #4 -x+1, -y+2, -z, #5 -x+2, -y+1, -z+1.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O.*Infrared :*

The experimental and theoretical IR spectra of [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O is shown in Fig. 4 asymmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of the coordinated carboxylate group^{30,31}, $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ at 1634 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ at 1384 cm⁻¹. The presence of strong sharp band in the range 1673–1750 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to a (C=O) vibration³². The presence of uncoordinated water, $\nu(\text{OH})$ in complex is indicated by broad band at 3425 cm⁻¹³³. In this complex a strong band at 266–280 cm⁻¹ is observed corresponding to the (Cu–N) of pyridine³⁴.

Electronic spectral properties and TD-DFT calculations :

To simulate the experimental electronic spectra, TD-

Table 4. Cyclic voltammetric data for [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O mmol L⁻¹ solution of the copper(II) complexes in DMSO containing 0.1 mol L⁻¹ TBAP as supporting electrolytes

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pc} (μA)	E_{pa} (mV)	I_{pa} (μA)	ΔE_p (mV)	$E^{o'}$ (mV)
[Cu(2-pca) ₂].2H ₂ O						
100	-890	1.9927	-149	0.1342	741	-519.5
200	-946	2.4362	-123	0.3012	823	-534.5
300	-969	4.3241	-113	0.6860	856	-541.0

$$\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}; E^{o'} = (E_{pa} + E_{pc})/2$$

EPR spectra :

The X-band EPR spectra of this complex in polycrystalline state at room temperature and in frozen DMSO solution at 77 K were recorded. The EPR spectra of the complex provide information about the coordination environment around the copper(II) in the complex. The polycrystalline and frozen solution sample yields axial type ($g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0$) spectra and suggest a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state for Cu^{II} in a square based geometry²⁸. Further, the $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ quotient²⁹ ranges from 105 to 135 cm for square planar copper(II) complexes. The $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ quotient of the present complex is in the same range and is suggestive of square planar geometry of the present complex.

TD-DFT/B3LYP/LANL2DZ calculations for ligand and complexes [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O have been performed in DMSO. The calculated vertical excitation energies oscillator strength and tentative nature of the transition obtained at the TD-DFT level have been presented in Tables 5 and 6. The absorption band at 295 nm for ligand is due to the six high energy excitations at 3.545, 3.752, 4.254, 4.272, 4.306 and 4.587 eV. These excitation states are contribution of $\beta\text{HOMO}-1 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (32%), $\beta\text{HOMO} \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (46%), $\beta\text{HOMO}-1 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}+1$ (31%), $\beta\text{HOMO}-3 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (20%), $\beta\text{HOMO}-2 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (30%), and $\beta\text{HOMO}-3 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (16%) transitions are given in Fig. 5. The complex [Cu(2-

Fig. 4. Comparison between experimental and theoretical IR spectra of $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Table 5. TD-DFT calculated excitations approximate assignments for L

Excitation (eV)	Wavelength (nm)	Oscillator strength (f)	Major contribution	Expt. wavelength (nm)
3.5452	349.72	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO}-1 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (32%)	–
3.7524	330.41	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO} \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (46%)	–
4.2546	291.41	0.0017	$\beta\text{HOMO} \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (48%)	295
4.2726	290.18	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO}-3 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (20%)	–
4.3069	287.88	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO}-2 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (30%)	–
4.5873	270.27	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO}-3 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (16%)	–
			$\beta\text{HOMO}-1 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}+1$ (31%)	–

Table 6. TD-DFT calculated excitations approximate assignments for $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Excitation (eV)	Wavelength (nm)	Oscillator strength (f)	Major contribution	Exp. wavelength (nm)
2.1764	569.66	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO}-2 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (67%)	623
2.4744	501.08	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO}-1 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (23%)	–
2.7059	458.20	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO}-1 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (14%)	–
2.8063	441.81	0.0000	$\beta\text{HOMO}-8 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (40%)	–
3.0469	406.92	0.0001	$\beta\text{HOMO} \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}+1$ (5%)	–
3.0738	403.36	0.0325	$\beta\text{HOMO} \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (95%)	–

$\text{pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows a well resolved absorption band at 623 nm^{15,35,36} appears to be composition of six excitation (Fig. 6) at 2.1764, 2.4744, 2.7059, 2.8063, 3.0469 and 3.0738 eV respectively, these excitation are contributed to $\beta\text{HOMO}-2 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (67%), $\beta\text{HOMO}-1 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (23.57%), $\beta\text{HOMO}-1 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (14.13%), $\beta\text{HOMO}-8 \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (40.99%), $\beta\text{HOMO} \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}+2$ (5.53%) and $\beta\text{HOMO} \rightarrow \beta\text{LUMO}$ (95.04%) which may be assigned

to d-d/LMCT/ILCT/LLCT charge transfer transitions. The experimental and theoretical UV-Visible spectrums are shown in Fig. 7.

Frontier molecular orbitals analysis :

The geometries of the ligand and complex are optimized in the singlet ground state is given in Fig. 8. The partial frontier molecular orbital compositions and energy

Fig. 5. HOMO-LUMO energy level diagram with their energy difference of 2-pca.

levels of all the complexes in the HOMO orbital primarily acts as an electron donor and the LUMO electron acceptor. Positive and negative region phase are represented in red and green colour respectively. The energy gap between HOMO and LUMO is the characteristic of molecular stability^{37,38}. Four important molecular orbitals, second highest HOMO-1 and highest occupied MO's HOMO the lowest LUMO and second lowest unoccupied MO's

LUMO+1 have been worked out for ligand (L) and complex [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O as -0.28909, -0.27061, -0.04433, -0.02758, -0.25126, -0.23612, -0.15722 and -0.13722 a.u., respectively. The energy gaps (ΔE) between HOMO-LUMO and HOMO-1-LUMO+1, for ligand and complex are -0.22628, -0.26151, -0.0789 and -0.11404 a.u., respectively. The LUMO orbitals of ligand and complex exhibit a large number of nodes than the HOMO orbitals.

Fig. 6. HOMO-LUMO energy level diagram with their energy difference of $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The energy of the frontier orbitals for molecules in terms of ionization energy (IE) and electron affinity (EA) of the ligand and complex from Koopmans's theorem³⁹ are :

$$-E_{\text{HOMO}} = \text{IE} \quad (2)$$

$$-E_{\text{LUMO}} = \text{EA} \quad (3)$$

The absolute electronegativity (χ_{abs}) and absolute hardness (η) are related to IE and EA⁴⁰ as given below :

$$\chi_{\text{abs}} = (\text{IE} + \text{EA})/2 = (E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}})/2 \quad (4)$$

$$\eta = (\text{IE} - \text{EA})/2 = (E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}})/2 \quad (5)$$

$$S = 1/\eta \quad (6)$$

Fig. 7. Comparison between experimental and theoretical UV-Visible spectra of $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 9. Spin density plot of $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 8. Optimized structures of 2-pca (a) and $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (b).

Hard molecules have a large HOMO–LUMO gap and soft molecules have a small HOMO–LUMO gap⁴¹. The absolute electronegativity (χ_{abs}), absolute hardness (η) and global softness (S), of ligand and complex are calculated using eqs. (4), (5) and (6). The values of the parameters are also calculated and presented in Table 7. The HOMO–LUMO structure with energy-level diagram of ligand and complex are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Spin density plot of the complex spread over 63% Cu, 20% coordinated O, 15% N and 2% uncoordinated O atom (Fig. 9).

Atomic charge analysis :

The natural atomic charge studies of (2-pca) and $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are obtained by NBO and Mulliken popula-

Compounds	χ_{abs}	η	S
Ligand (2-pca)	-0.15747	-0.11314	-8.83
$[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-0.19667	-0.03945	-25.34

tion analysis⁴². Atomic charge distribution on donor-acceptor atoms of the studied complexes and donor atoms of free ligands were calculated at B3LYP/LANL2DZ level of theory. Charge distributions between donor atoms of ligand and acceptor atoms of complexes were evaluated by NBO and Mulliken in gas phase. The charge distribution results of 2-pca and $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are listed in Table 8. Comparing the atomic charges in Table 8, it can be observed that the electron density of the donor atoms in the complexes decreased as compared to that in the free ligand, while the electron density of copper(II) cation increased. For instance, before complexation, the charge on copper is +2, while the charge of copper in $[\text{Cu}(2\text{-pca})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is +0.865452. This indicates that ligand transfer their negative charges to copper(II) ions during formation of complexes. The graphically representation of charge of before complexation of copper(II) and after complexation with ligand is shown in Fig. 10.

Molecular surface electrostatic potential of ligand and complex :

The molecular surface electrostatic potential (MSEP) surface diagram is used to understand the reactive behavior of a molecule, in that negative regions can be regarded as nucleophilic centers, whereas the positive regions are potential electrophilic sites. The molecular electrostatic potential surface^{43,44} (Fig. 11) displays molecular shape, size, and electrostatic potential values of ligand and complex. The MSEP map of ligand shows that the carboxylate oxygens represent the most negative potential region, while in the case of the complex, the coordination environment of two nitrogen and two oxygens copper (central

Table 8. Data of Mulliken, NBO atomic charges and spin density of [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O

No.	Atomic	Mulliken		NBO		Spin densities [Cu(2-pca) ₂].2H ₂ O
		[Cu(2-pca) ₂].2H ₂ O	(2-pca)	[Cu(2-pca) ₂].2H ₂ O	(2-pca)	
1.	Cu	0.865452	+2	1.06146	+2	0.636387
2.	C	-0.057113	-0.228419	-0.19267	-0.21403	-0.006013
3.	C	-0.118018	-0.178834	-0.26278	-0.18508	0.010908
4.	C	0.163574	-0.143837	0.12722	-0.21549	-0.012848
5.	N	-0.603036	-0.110785	-0.53791	-0.51155	0.075120
6.	C	0.281599	-0.279296	0.07162	0.02071	-0.000711
7.	C	-0.118638	-0.018974	-0.19600	0.14558	0.003872
8.	C	0.602111	0.233802	0.76786	0.79893	-0.000914
9.	O	-0.489745	-0.246188	-0.58407	-0.56502	0.003409
10.	O	-0.676332	-0.426464	-0.78498	-0.71293	0.106711

Fig. 10. Graphical representation of Mulliken, NBO atomic charge and spin density plot of (2-pca) and [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O.

atom) is the region of less negative potential. Potential increases in the order red < orange < yellow < green < blue. The negative (red, orange and yellow) regions of the MEP are related to electrophilic reactivity. The maximum negative region is localized over the O of carboxylate ions and the maximum positive region is localized on N pyridal group, indicating a possible site for nucleophilic attack. These sites give information about the region from which the compound has intermolecular interactions.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity :

The SOD activity of complex was investigated by the NBT assay method and the catalytic activity towards the dismutation of the superoxide anion was measured by the literature method^{45,46}. Superoxide dismutation is a redox process. The IC₅₀ value for SOD activity has been defined as the chromophore concentration required to yield 50% inhibition of the reduction of NBT. The IC₅₀ values of the present copper complex is found to be 18 μmol. The present complex showed SOD activity, but are less

Fig. 11. MEP plot of (a) 2-pca and (b) [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O.

active than the native SOD (IC₅₀ = 0.04 μM). The kinetic catalytic constants (K_{MCCF})^{47,48} of [Cu(2-pca)₂].2H₂O is 18.48 × 10⁻⁴ M⁻¹ s⁻¹. The activities of these complexes may be attributed to the flexible nature of the ligand (2-pca) used, which is able to accommodate the geometrical change from copper(II) to copper(I)⁴⁷ in the catalytic process, just like O₂⁻ in place of the water molecule bound to the copper site in the mechanism of dismutation of O₂⁻ by native SOD.

Experimental

Materials :

Copper(II) acetate hexahydrate, and 2-pca were purchased from Across Organics. All other chemicals were of synthetic grade and used as received.

Synthesis of complexes :

The complexes were prepared by the following general procedures : $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to an MeOH solution (20 mL) $\text{Cu}(\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.199 g, 1.0 mmol) an MeOH solution (20 mL) of 2-pca (0.246 g, 2.0 mmol) was added with stirring for 30 min at 25 °C. The resulting blue solution was allowed to slowly concentrate by evaporation at RT for 3 days. A blue microcrystalline solid deposited was collected by filtration, washed with methanol and stored in CaCl_2 desiccators at RT. Anal. Found (%) : C, 41.25; H, 3.50; N, 8.45; Cu, 18.40. Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{CuO}_6$: C, 41.92; H, 3.52; N, 8.15; Cu, 18.48; O, 27.92; FAB mass (m/z) : Obsd. (Calcd.) 343.70 (343.779).

Physical measurements :

FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA 6000 Mass Spectrometer using xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at RT with *m*-nitrobenzoyl alcohol as the matrix. RT magnetic susceptibilities were measured by the Gouy balance using a mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units). Diamagnetic corrections were estimated from Pascal tables. Ligand-field spectra were recorded at 25 °C on a Shimadzu UV-Vis recording Spectrophotometer UV-1601 in solution. Infrared (IR) spectra were recorded in KBr medium on a Perkin-Elmer 783 Spectrophotometer. Cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a BAS-100 Epsilon electrochemical analyzer having an electrochemical cell with a three-electrode system. Ag/AgCl was used as reference electrode, glassy carbon as working electrode, and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode. TBAP (0.5 mol L⁻¹) was used as supporting electrolyte in DMSO. All measurements were carried out at 298 K under nitrogen. The solution was deoxygenated by purging nitrogen gas.

The *in vitro* superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity was measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical (O_2^-) and nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT) chloride as

O_2^- scavenger¹⁶. In general, 400 mL sample to be assayed was added to a solution containing 2.1 mL of 0.2 mol L⁻¹ potassium phosphate buffer (pH 8.6) and 1 mL of 56 mmol L⁻¹ alkaline DMSO solution was added while stirring. The absorbance was then monitored at 540 nm against a sample prepared under similar condition except NaOH was absent in DMSO. A unit of SOD activity is the concentration of complex, which causes 50% inhibition of alkaline DMSO mediated reduction of NBT.

Crystals suitable for single-crystal X-ray analysis for $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was grown from slow evaporation of the reaction mixtures at RT in CH_3OH . Single crystals of $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ suitable for X-ray study were mounted on a glass fiber and used for data collection. The crystal orientation, cell refinement, and intensity measurements were made using CAD-4PC performing scan measurements. Data were collected with Bruker X8 Proteum diffractometers. The data for $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was processed with APEX2 and corrected for absorption using SADABS. The structures were solved by direct methods using SHELXS-97¹⁷ and refined by full-matrix least-squares against F2 using SHELXL-97¹⁸. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. All hydrogens were geometrically fixed and allowed to refine using a riding model.

Computational method :

The input file of the copper(II) complexes were prepared with Gauss View 5.0.9¹⁹. All calculation were made using GUASSIAN09 packag program²⁰ by the DFT/B3LYP method. LANL2DZ and 6-31G(d,p) are the standard basic sets. 6-31G(d,p) is a popular polarized basis set which adds p functions to hydrogen atoms in addition to the d functions on heavy atoms, while LANL2DZ is a basis set for post-third-row atoms. In the computational model, the nitrate and perchlorate anion was ignored and the monocationic complex was taken into account. The electronic spectrum was predicted by calculating the excitation energy between the states. Electronic spectrum calculations of the complexes were made by using time dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT)/B3LYP method with LANL2DZ basis set in gas phase²¹. Franck-Condon electronic excitation spectra were calculated on the optimized structures both in vacuum and in DMSO using the polarized continuum model (PCM)²² within the Time Dependent-Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) taking into account the lowest 30 excitations.

Conclusions

We have synthesized $[\text{Cu}(\text{2-pca})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex and this was characterized by various physicochemical techniques. The present study highlights that the spectroscopy data together with redox behaviour may be regarded as an index for constructing a potentially feasible structural model of copper containing metallo-proteins. The geometrical parameters of the title compound are in agreement with experimental XRD results. This complex also showed superoxide dismutase activity.

Supplementary material

The X-ray crystallographic data for the structures reported in this article have been deposited at the CCDC as supplementary data CCDC No. 1416091. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structure-summary-form> the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk and Supplementary data Table S1.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to acknowledge the assistance of Dr. Matthias Zeller in the collection of diffraction data and NSF Grant CHE 0087210, Ohio Board of Regents Grant CAP-491, and by Youngstown State University for funds to purchase the X-ray diffractometer for single crystal data collection. The Head, RSIC, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow is also thankfully acknowledged for providing analytical and spectral facilities. Financial assistance from MPCST [Scheme No. A/RD/RP-2/2015-16/245]. We also acknowledge the Department of Chemistry, APS University, Rewa (Madhya Pradesh), India for providing laboratory facilities and theoretical calculations.

References

1. A. Caneschi, D. Catteschi, J. P. Renard, P. Ray and R. Sessoli, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 785.
2. C. Oldham, "Carboxylates, squarates and related species", in : ed. G. Wilkinson, 'Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry', Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1987, Chap. 15.6.
3. B. Zurowska, J. Ochocki, Z. Ciunik, J. Mrozinski and J. Reedijk, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **357**, 755.
4. B. Zurowska and J. Mrozinski, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2003, **342**, 23.
5. B. Zurowska, J. Mrozinski and Z. Ciunik, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 1211.
6. L. Ouahab, *Chem. Mater.*, 1997, **9**, 1909.
7. K. Jitsukawa, K. Iwai, H. Masuda, H. Ogoshi and H. Einaga, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 3691.
8. T. Sugimori, H. Masuda, N. Ohata, K. Koiwai, A. Odani and O. Yamauchi, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1997, **36**, 576.
9. G. W. Evans, *Int. J. Biosoc. Med. Res.*, 1989, **11**, 163.
10. G. W. Evans, "Picolinates : How They Help Build Muscle Without Steroids and Other Health Benefits", Keats Publishing, New Canaan, CT, 1989.
11. J. Jayabharathi, V. Thanikachalam and M. V. Perumal, *Spectrochem. Acta, Part A*, 2012, **95**, 614.
12. P. Segl'a, M. Jamnický, M. Koman, J. Šima and T. Glowiak, *Polyhedron*, 1998, **17**, 4525.
13. D. Dutta, A. D. Jana, A. Ray, J. Marek and M. Ali, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2008, **47A**, 1656.
14. H. H. Monfared, M. Vahedpour, M. M. Yeganeh, M. Ghorbanloo, P. Mayer and C. Janiak, *Dalton Trans.*, 2011, **40**, 1286.
15. R. N. Patel, V. P. Sondhiya, K. K. Shukla, D. K. Patel and Y. Singh, *Polyhedron*, 2013, **50**, 139.
16. R. N. Patel, V. L. N. Gundla and D. K. Patel, *Polyhedron*, 2008, **27**, 1054.
17. G. M. Sheldrick. *Acta Crystallogr., Sect. A*, 1990, **46**, 467.
18. G. M. Sheldrick. SHELXL-97, Program for the Refinement of Crystal Structures, University of Göttingen, Germany, 1997.
19. Gauss View 5.0.9, Gaussian Inc., Wallingford CT, USA, 2009.
20. Gaussian 09, Revision D.01, M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Caricato, X. Li, H. P. Hratchian, A. F. Izmaylov, J. Bloino, G. Zheng, J. L. Sonnenberg, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T. Vreven, J. A. Montgomery (Jr.), J. E. Peralta, F. Ogliaro, M. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E. Brothers, K. N. Kudin, V. N. Staroverov, T. Keith, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A. Rendell, J. C. Burant, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, N. Rega, J. M. Millam, M. Klene, J. E. Knox, J. B. Cross, V. Bakken, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, R. L. Martin, K. Morokuma, V. G. Zakrzewski, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, O. Farkas, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, J. Cioslowski and D. J. Fox, Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford CT, 2013.
21. A. E. Reed, R. B. Weinstock and F. Weinhold, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **83**, 735.
22. V. Barone, M. Cossi and J. Tomasi, *J. Comput.*

- Chem.*, 1998, **19**, 404.
23. M. Melnik, M. Kabešáová, M. Dunaj-Jurčo and C. E. Holloway, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1997, **41**, 35.
24. M. E. Bluhm, M. Ciesielski, H. Gorls, O. Walter and M. Doring, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 8878.
25. H. Masuda, A. Odani and O. Yamauchi, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 624.
26. B. Zurowska, J. Mrozinski and K. Slepokura, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 3379.
27. Y. Nako, W. Mori, T. Sakurai and A. Nakahara, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1981, **55**, 103.
28. B. J. Hathway and D. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143.
29. M. M. Taquikhan, D. Chatterji, R. R. Merchant, P. Paul, S. H. R. Abdi, D. Srinivas, M. R. H. Siddiqui, M. A. Moiz, M. M. Bhodbhade and K. V. Bramanaia, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 2711.
30. G. B. Deacon and R. J. Philips, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **33**, 227.
31. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1997.
32. J. Borrás, G. Alznet, M. Gonzatez-Alvarez, F. Estevan, B. Macias, M. Liu-Gonzatez and A. Castiñeiras, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 5009.
33. K. Nakamoto, M. Margoshes and R. E. Rundle, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 6480.
34. R. J. Clark and C. S. Williams, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 350.
35. S. Mandal, B. Nasar, R. Modak, Y. Sikdar, S. Chatterjee, S. Biswas, T. K. Mondal, D. Modak and S. Goswami, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2015, **1088**, 38.
36. T. G. Fawcett, E. E. Bernarducci, K. K. Jespersen and H. J. Schugar, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 2598.
37. D. Shoba, S. Periandy, M. Karabacak and S. Ramalingam, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2011, **83**, 540.
38. K. Fukui, *Science*, 1982, **218**, 747.
39. C. J. Brabec, N. S. Sariciftci and J. C. Hummelen, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2001, **11**, 15.
40. E. Ebenso, T. Arslan, F. Kandemirl, I. Love, M. Saracoglu and S. A. Umoren, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 2010, **110**, 2614.
41. R. G. Pearson, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1993, **26**, 250.
42. R. S. Mulliken, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1995, **23**, 1833.
43. Y. Sun, X. Chen, L. Sun, X. Guo and W. Lu, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2003, **381**, 397.
44. O. Christiansen, J. Gauss and J. F. Stanton, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1999, **305**, 147.
45. R. G. Bhirud and T. S. Shrivastava, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1990, **40**, 331.
46. R. N. Patel, S. Kumar and K. B. Pandeya, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2002, **89**, 61.
47. R. F. Pasternack and B. Halliwell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 1026.
48. Z. R. Liao, X. F. Zheng, B. S. Luo, L. R. Shen, D. F. Li, H. L. Liu and W. Zhao, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 2813.